

GENERATING OPTIMAL PATHS IN DYNAMIC ENVIRONMENTS USING RIVER FORMATION DYNAMICS ALGORITHM

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Abstract

The paper presents a comparison of four optimisation algorithms implemented for the purpose of finding the shortest path in static and dynamic environments with obstacles. Two classical graph algorithms — the Dijkstra complete algorithm and A* heuristic algorithm — were compared with metaheuristic River Formation Dynamics swarm algorithm and its newly introduced modified version. Moreover, another swarm algorithm has been compared — the Ant Colony Optimization and its modification. Terms and conditions of the simulation are thoroughly explained, paying special attention to the new, modified River Formation Dynamics algorithm. The algorithms were used for the purpose of generating the shortest path in three different types of environments, each served as a static environment and as a dynamic environment with changing goal or changing obstacles. The results show that the proposed modified River Formation Dynamics algorithm is efficient in finding the shortest path, especially when compared to its original version. In cases where the path should be adjusted to changes in the environment, calculations carried out by the proposed algorithm are faster than the A*, Dijkstra, and Ant Colony Optimization algorithms. This advantage is even more evident the more complex and extensive the environment is.

1 Introduction

Path planning relates to the problem of calculating a continuous or discrete path in a known or unknown environment in such a way, that the path will not violate any established constraints. An object guided along the path should achieve its goal while avoiding collision with any encountered obstacles. This process is most frequently implemented with an additional path length optimisation. However, energy consumption, time of travel or other physical factors are often subjected to an optimisation process as well.

Most often this issue is encountered in navigation systems for autonomous vehicles where safe and efficient passage is crucial and its efficiency is measured by path length (the shortest possible) and calculation time (also taking into account time to adapt to changes during the passage). As nearly all real-world applications are subject to, often very frequent, changes, the ability to rapidly correct itself according to the given changes plays a crucial role in all path planning systems.

30 The issue of computing an efficient path was repeatedly discussed in various contexts [1, 2].
31 Current solutions are based on two major principles: on classical, iterative methods, such as the
32 Dijkstra's algorithm [3], and on heuristic methods [4, 5]. The classical approach is computationally
33 simple, however offers limited possibilities for more complex cases. Methods based on heuristic
34 algorithms provide more flexibility for coping with multi-objective, complicated problems. In
35 addition, heuristics are well suited for solving NP-complete problems, which are the case in
36 path finding tasks, especially with time, velocity, and acceleration restrictions among polyhedral
37 obstacles [6, 7].

38 Today the issue of moving in a known environment based on a complete map does not pose
39 a major research problem. On the other hand navigation in an area partially or completely
40 unknown or with dynamically moving obstacles and/or goals is still a problem not fully explored.
41 This is particularly evident if one takes into account the latest artificial intelligence methods,
42 such as swarm algorithms, to generate collision-free trajectories under uncertainty while dealing
43 with possible terrain variations.

44 Employment of heuristic methods, e.g. the D* algorithm [8, 9], provides good results, however
45 some of the methods suffer from high computation times (which eliminates their use for rapidly
46 changing conditions), or from lack of adjustment to measurement uncertainty. Research on the
47 D* algorithm for path planning in unknown, partially known, and completely known environment
48 shows that even with very limited knowledge about the environment (approx. 1/64 of the whole
49 map) the costs of passage were maintained only at a slightly higher level than for a completely
50 known environment [8]. By further modifications of the D* algorithm, a 96% computation time
51 reduction was achieved [9]. Another heuristic method – the A* algorithm – was used to generate
52 collision-free trajectories in real-time for dynamic unknown environments [10]. By generating
53 intermediate targets that depend on execution time and current values of sensory signals, the
54 algorithm was able to generate collision-free paths in real time, even in large-scale, dynamic,
55 unknown environments. However, the algorithm could not cope with re-planning of (upgrading)
56 the paths.

57 So far, swarm algorithms were successfully used to solve the problem of static programming, i.
58 e. when the map is known [11, 12]. A comparison between Dijkstra's algorithm, modified Dijkstra's
59 algorithm, and a combined Dijkstra's and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm was
60 made for generating collision-free paths for a fixed, unchanging environment [11]. It was proved
61 that the PSO algorithm poses higher potential for generating shorter motion paths than the
62 other presented methods. Zhang et al. [12] proposed a two-stage optimisation algorithm for path
63 selection risk and length of the path. The PSO algorithm was used to optimise both functions
64 and the results showed acceptable and safe motion paths for four three-dimensional environments
65 affected by uncertainty, with static obstacles varying in number, location, and shape.

66 There is a limited number of studies on the use of other nature-inspired algorithms, like Genetic
67 Algorithms [13, 14] or Simulated Annealing algorithm [15], as an effective tool for dynamic path
68 optimisation. In complex environments, Genetic Algorithms consume a lot of time to generate
69 collision-free trajectories, which limits their practical use. It was shown that for an environment
70 with fourteen static and five dynamic obstacles, a system based on Genetic Algorithms needed
71 about 10 seconds to find the first valid path [13]. Better results were observed in the case
72 of the Simulated Annealing algorithm, where its enhanced version demonstrated a significant
73 advantage over compared algorithms in speed of generating a collision-free trajectory in complex
74 environments [15]. Another nature-inspired algorithm – Random Particle Path Optimization
75 – was compared with a classical path planning method – Artificial Potential Field [16]. It was
76 concluded that the proposed algorithm can generate shorter paths even in an environment with
77 moving obstacles and varying goals.

78 As mentioned above, the issue of effective motion planning under dynamic conditions (i.e. with

79 variable terrain and objectives) remains a matter that needs to be addressed. Nature-inspired
80 algorithms, with swarm algorithms in particular, are means to solve even most complicated
81 problems with varying conditions, while still being effectively fast and robust. Due to increasing
82 number of new swarm algorithms it is crucial to examine their potentiality to solve the given
83 problem, as most of the literature focuses on implementing the Particle Swarm Optimization or
84 Ant Colony Optimization algorithms.

85 One of the latest methods in this field of computation is the River Formation Dynamics
86 (RFD) algorithm [17]. It is based on an idea to imitate the process of riverbed formation, and
87 as an optimisation algorithm it surpasses even the Ant Colony Optimization [18, 19]. Moreover,
88 there are indications that this algorithm is efficient in robot motion planning [20], however its
89 features have not been thoroughly researched. Bearing in mind those facts, a question is raised
90 whether the RFD algorithm can be used to effectively generate optimal paths in dynamically
91 changing conditions, especially when compared to more established methods. Therefore this
92 article aims at presenting the RFD algorithm in the task of dynamic motion planning, as well
93 as introduces all necessary improvements to the algorithm's core. To measure its effectiveness,
94 the original and modified versions of the RFD algorithm are compared with the Ant Colony
95 Optimization algorithm together with its modified version and two classical Dijkstra's [21] and
96 A* [22] algorithms by their optimised path length and computation time.

97 2 Methods

98 2.1 River Formation Dynamics algorithm

99 The principle of the RFD algorithm is to imitate the process of formation of riverbeds. A set of
100 drops placed at the starting point is subjected to gravitational forces that attract the drops to
101 the centre of the earth. As a result, these drops are distributed throughout their environment,
102 seeking the lowest point – the sea. Riverbeds with many meanders are formed in this process.
103 The RFD utilises this idea in graph theory problems. A set of agents-drops are created and move
104 on edges between nodes, exploring an environment for the best solution. This is accomplished by
105 mechanisms of erosion and soil sedimentation that relate to changes in altitude that is assigned to
106 each node. Drops, when moving throughout an environment, modify node altitudes along their
107 path. The transition from one node to another is carried out according to decreasing gradient of
108 the nodes, which in fact provides many benefits (e.g., avoidance of local cycles) [17]. The RFD
109 algorithm in this manner is a gradient-oriented variant of the Ant Colony Optimization algorithm.

110 A brief description of the RFD algorithm is as follows. An amount of soil is assigned to each
111 node. Drops, as they move, erode their paths (taking some soil from nodes) or deposit the carried
112 sediment (thus increasing the altitudes of nodes). Probability of choosing the next node depends
113 on the gradient, which is proportional to the difference between height of the node at which the
114 drop resides and height of its neighbour. In the beginning the environment is flat, i.e. altitudes of
115 all nodes are equal, except the goal node which is equal to zero during the entire process. Drops
116 are placed in the initial node to enable further exploration of the environment. At each step
117 a group of drops sequentially traverses the space, and then performs erosion on visited nodes.
118 Algorithm 1 presents the RFD algorithm in a form of a pseudo-code.

119 Drops move one at a time (line 5), until they reach the goal or are unable to make a move, in
120 which case they evaporate to start over in a new iteration. The probability $P_k(i, j)$ that a drop k

Algorithm 1 River Formation Dynamics algorithm

- 1: Place all drops in starting node
 - 2: Height of nodes \leftarrow initial height
 - 3: Height of target node $\leftarrow 0$
 - 4: **while** end conditions are not met **do**
 - 5: Move all drops across the graph
 - 6: Analyse complete paths
 - 7: Height of nodes on paths $--$ erosion based on path costs
 - 8: Height of all nodes $++$ small amount of sediment
 - 9: **end while**
-

121 residing in node i would select the next node j is as follows:

$$P_k(i, j) = \begin{cases} \frac{\text{gradient}(i, j)}{\text{total}} & \text{for } j \in V_k(i) \\ \frac{\omega/|\text{gradient}(i, j)|}{\text{total}} & \text{for } j \in U_k(i) \\ \frac{\delta}{\text{total}} & \text{for } j \in F_k(i) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

122 where

$$\text{gradient}(i, j) = \frac{\text{altitude}(i) - \text{altitude}(j)}{\text{distance}(i, j)} \quad (2)$$

123

$$\begin{aligned} \text{total} = & \left(\sum_{l \in V_k(i)} \text{gradient}(i, l) \right) + \\ & + \left(\sum_{l \in U_k(i)} \frac{\omega}{|\text{gradient}(i, l)|} \right) + \\ & + \left(\sum_{l \in F_k(i)} \delta \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

124 $V_k(i)$ is a set of neighbouring nodes with a positive gradient (node i has a higher altitude than
125 node j), $U_k(i)$ is a set of neighbouring nodes with a negative gradient (altitude of node j is
126 higher), and $F_k(i)$ represents neighbours with a flat gradient. Coefficients ω and δ are certain
127 small fixed values.

128 After all drops move, an erosion process is executed on all travelled paths by reducing altitudes
129 of nodes in proportion to their gradient with a successive node (line 7). The erosion amount
130 for each pair of nodes i and j (Equation (4)) also depends on the number of all used drops D ,
131 number of all nodes in the graph N , and a certain erosion coefficient E .

132 Additionally, if a drop failed to choose a subsequent node to transition onto, it deposits a
133 fraction of carried sediment and evaporates for the rest of the algorithm iteration. This reduces
134 the likelihood of transition to blind alleys, hence weakening bad paths.

$$\text{erosion}(i, j) = \frac{E}{(N - 1) \cdot D} \cdot \text{gradient}(i, j) \quad (4)$$

135 After each iteration a certain, small amount of sediment is added to all nodes (line 8) in order to
136 avoid a situation where all altitudes are close to zero, which would make gradients negligible and

137 would ruin all formed paths. The formula for the sediment to be added is presented in Equation
 138 (5).

$$sediment = \frac{erosionProduced}{N - 1} \quad (5)$$

139 The algorithm is executed until the final condition is reached. This condition may represent all
 140 drops moving on the same path. Additionally, in order to reduce computation time, a top limit
 141 on the number of iterations can be introduced, as well as a condition verifying if the solution has
 142 not been improved by the last n loops.

143 2.2 Modified River Formation Dynamics algorithm

144 The original RFD algorithm has certain drawbacks which prevent the algorithm from performing
 145 well in the described path generation problem [20]. Because of a large number of coefficients,
 146 tuning of the algorithm to a particular case is highly unintuitive. And even despite this, its
 147 convergence rate is small for more complicated environments.

148 Because of the above, this article introduces the modified RFD algorithm. The algorithm is
 149 modified so that the formula for the transition probability for the next node to be selected is based
 150 on an exponential function. A large number of additional RFD coefficients strongly influence
 151 the algorithm's efficiency for a specific problem. Their values are difficult to tune properly. By
 152 changing the formula, this problem is disposed off. In addition, distance from the objective
 153 node heuristic is added (as in the A* algorithm). Equation (6) presents the modified probability
 154 formula and its exemplary results are presented in Figure 1. It is based on two coefficients: $pBase$,
 155 which is the base for the exponent, and α , which is a convergence tuning coefficient. The d_j
 156 indicates Cartesian distance from node j to the goal.

$$P_k(i, j) = \frac{pBase^{gradient(i,j)}}{(d_j)^\alpha} / total, \quad (6)$$

$$total = \sum_{l \in V_k(i) \cup U_k(i) \cup F_k(i)} \frac{pBase^{gradient(i,l)}}{(d_l)^\alpha}$$

157 As can be seen in Figure 1, the probability values are uniformly distributed from very low
 158 values for negative gradients to rapidly increasing values for positive gradients. A flat gradient is
 159 assigned with a fixed value (1 in this case). It is more intuitive to tune the exponent base value
 160 for a particular case, bearing in mind how rapidly the probability should increase with increasing
 161 gradient, and what would be the maximum gradient value. The same formula can be applied to
 162 the erosion values.

163 2.3 Ant Colony Optimization

164 Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) developed by Dorigo et al. [23] is one of the first optimisation
 165 techniques inspired by the intelligence of animal swarms. The source of its inspiration was the
 166 behaviour of ant colonies, especially the mechanism of their communication. The ACO algorithm
 167 is mainly used in graph problems where it was proved to be highly efficient. The Ant System
 168 algorithm is one of the basic algorithms derived from the ACO techniques group. Algorithm 2
 169 presents the Ant System algorithm in a form of a pseudo-code.

170 In each iteration, agents-ants start at the initial node. For an ant k located in node i , selection
 171 of the next node j is made according to the following likelihood:

Figure 1: Probability of selecting the next node based on its gradient for three base values.

Algorithm 2 Ant Colony Optimization algorithm

- 1: Assign m agents to the start node.
 - 2: Assign a certain initial amount of pheromone to each edge of the graph.
 - 3: **while** end conditions are not met **do**
 - 4: Construct a path for each agent.
 - 5: Update the amount of pheromone on each edge.
 - 6: **end while**
 - 7: Save the best path.
-

$$P_k(i, j) = \begin{cases} \frac{\tau_{i,j}}{\sum_{l \in N_k(i)} \tau_{i,l}} & \text{if } j \in N_k(i) \\ 0 & \text{if } j \notin N_k(i) \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

172 where $N_k(i)$ is a set of nodes connected to the edges of the node in which the ant k is located,
 173 and $\tau_{i,j}$ is the amount of pheromone on the edge between nodes i and j .

174 Each selected node is saved in a local solution S . Upon reaching the end, an ant returns to
 175 the starting node while changing the amount of pheromone on edges contained in the solution S .
 176 This change is inversely proportional to the value of the objective function $f(S)$, i.e. the length
 177 of the travelled path. In addition, a positive factor Q is introduced. The formula for updating
 178 the amount of pheromone on a single edge between node i and j is as follows:

$$\tau_{i,j} \leftarrow \tau_{i,j} + \frac{Q}{f(S)} \quad (8)$$

179 To simulate the process of volatilization of pheromones, the mechanism of evaporation is
 180 introduced. It prevents formation of very large differences between successive edges. The formula
 181 for the volatilization of pheromones on an edge is shown in the following equation:

$$\tau_{i,j} \leftarrow (1 - \rho) \cdot \tau_{i,j} \quad (9)$$

182 where ρ stands for an evaporation coefficient.

183 2.4 Environment representation

184 To apply the above mentioned algorithms in a path generation problem, the environment must
 185 be properly modelled. The model should be in a form of a graph with nodes being the access
 186 points, and edges representing all possible transitions.

187 Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph containing a set of vertices V and edges E , and $w : E \rightarrow$
 188 $\{1, 2, \dots\}$, $w \in \mathbb{R}_+$ be a function that assigns an edge weight to every single edge in G . An
 189 edge $(u, v) \in E$ is indicated by $u-v$ with $u, v \in V$, whereas its weight is indicated by w_{u-v} . The
 190 sequence of vertices $p = v_0, v_1, \dots, v_k$ is called a path in G if and only if $v_i - v_{i+1}$ is an edge in E
 191 for all $i = 0, 1, \dots, k - 1$. If edge weights represent distances between connected vertices, a sum
 192 of edge weights between consecutive vertices in the considered path p is $d = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} w_{v_i-v_{i+1}}$ and
 193 can be called a path length. The problem of path generation comes down to minimising the value
 194 of d for a path that connects the starting point to the goal.

195 This path represents successively selected nodes in the graph, the structure of which reflects
 196 the appearance of an environment. The model assumes the presence of obstacles (inaccessible
 197 nodes). The environments presented can be divided into $W \times H$ cells, thus a graph containing
 198 $W \cdot H$ nodes with proper edge connections can be its representation. Figure 2 presents such
 199 environment model for a 4×3 map. All nodes are connected by edges to their neighbours, unless
 200 an adjacent node is representing an obstacle.

201 Since the environment map is based on a rectangular picture, all graph nodes can be represented
 202 by pixels of this picture. Therefore, each node can have up to eight neighbours being the adjacent
 203 pixels. If a node is representing an obstacle its connections to all adjacent nodes are severed.

Figure 2: Representation of a 4×3 map points as a graph. Black nodes represent obstacles.

204 3 Results and discussion

205 This section presents a comparative study of five algorithms: Dijkstra's, A* (the two most popular
 206 graph algorithms, a complete one and heuristic), Ant Colony Optimization, a modified version of
 207 the Ant Colony Optimization (referred to as ACO*), River Formation Dynamics, and a modified

208 River Formation Dynamics algorithm (referred to as RFD*). The performance tests were carried
 209 out in three representative environments involving a large number of obstacles arranged in different
 210 configurations. Each environment was scaled to three different sizes: 20×20 , 50×50 , and 100×100
 211 cells, resulting in a total of nine test cases. A graphical representation of those three types of
 212 environments is shown in Figure 3.

213 The modified ACO algorithm was developed in a similar manner than the RFD* algorithm.
 214 That is, The probability of choosing the next node is divided by distance to the goal, as in the
 215 denominator in Eq. (6).

216 Points on maps that represent tested environments were translated into graphs according to
 217 Section 2.4. Coordinates of the starting point and the objective were as follows: $(0,0) \rightarrow (19,19)$
 218 for 20×20 maze, $(1,9) \rightarrow (18,9)$ for 20×20 mosaic, $(3,9) \rightarrow (16,9)$ for 20×20 alley, $(0,0) \rightarrow (49,49)$ for
 219 50×50 maze, $(2,24) \rightarrow (46,24)$ for 50×50 mosaic, $(9,24) \rightarrow (38,24)$ for 50×50 alley, $(0,0) \rightarrow (99,99)$
 220 for 100×100 maze, $(2,54) \rightarrow (97,54)$ for 100×100 mosaic, and $(23,49) \rightarrow (75,49)$ for 100×100 alley.

221 All results presented in the following tables summarise a series of twenty tests carried out for
 222 each case. For this purpose, a test model has been made using C# programming language. Test
 223 were carried out on a personal computer with an Intel Core i7-3770 CPU and 32 GB of RAM.
 224 The presented swarm algorithms were set to work for up to 100 iterations.

Figure 3: Graphical representation of environments used for the tests (obstacles marked black).
 a: maze. b: mosaic. c: alley.

225 Table 1 shows test results for a static environment, where both the starting point and
 226 destination are fixed during calculations. Records marked “n/a” indicate that for the given case
 227 an algorithm could not generate any correct path.

228 As can be seen from Table 1, the RFD and ACO algorithms failed to generate any correct
 229 path for the maze of all sizes. In other cases the algorithms have successfully found a path from
 230 the starting point to the objective. Path lengths computed by the Dijkstra’s algorithm may be
 231 regarded as the optimal ones (as this algorithm is bound to find optimal solutions, as long as
 232 such exist). Compared to it, the RFD algorithm has found paths longer than the optimum by
 233 about 1.61 (for the 20×20 mosaic) to 23.9 times (for the 100×100 alley). In the case of execution
 234 time the RFD algorithm performed likewise. Computation times were longer by about 70 (for
 235 environments of size of 100×100 cells) to 758 times (for environments of size of 20×20 cells) than
 236 the best performing A* algorithm. This proves that the RFD algorithm in its original form is
 237 not an alternative for the classical algorithms. This is mainly due to its poor convergence when
 238 operating on such an extensive graph while the transition costs are dependent only on distance of
 239 succeeding nodes. Moreover, values of coefficients of the RFD algorithm have a strong influence
 240 on its performance and must be adapted to a specific problem, however their tuning is highly
 241 unintuitive.

242 After introducing distance heuristic to the ACO algorithm, its performance increased. The

Table 1: Averaged path length and computation time of compared algorithms for static, invariable environments.

		Mosaic 20×20	Alley 20×20	Maze 20×20	Mosaic 50×50	Alley 50×50	Maze 50×50	Mosaic 100×100	Alley 100×100	Maze 100×100
Path length [-]	Dijkstra	18.65	33.48	78.62	50.62	81.97	228.52	116.94	170.42	510.56
	A*	18.65	33.48	78.62	50.62	81.97	228.52	116.94	170.42	510.56
	ACO	51.68	138.98	n/a	450.65	1158.61	n/a	2749.60	5435.08	n/a
	ACO*	18.65	87.49	n/a	55.16	181.56	n/a	211.98	379.15	n/a
	RFD	30.21	117.12	n/a	383.1	839.24	n/a	2196.57	4070.42	n/a
	RFD*	18.65	33.48	78.62	50.62	81.97	228.52	116.94	170.42	510.56
Computation time [ms]	Dijkstra	6.051	5.787	6.534	57.876	59.333	46.316	542.385	753.503	445.556
	A*	1.601	4.453	6.265	24.173	56.662	48.895	335.751	661.118	448.542
	ACO	650.16	681.82	n/a	10118.72	10086.02	n/a	131071.05	132445.70	n/a
	ACO*	71.481	662.063	n/a	4005.241	6078.251	n/a	38630.724	29628.093	n/a
	RFD	1213.59	1279.466	n/a	8121.88	8704.5	n/a	33653.09	46341.6	n/a
	RFD*	59.548	103.421	84.211	268.349	291.77	337.529	4172.388	5934.1	5108.49

243 additional heuristic improves convergence.

244 The modified RFD* algorithm has found the optimal path in all cases, however its computation
 245 times were still 5 to 37 times longer than the fastest obtained from the A* algorithm. Despite
 246 a considerable improvement with respect to the original RFD algorithm, its nature (heuristic
 247 calculations performed sequentially by many agents) hinders high-speed calculations for a com-
 248 pletely unknown environment. This disadvantage may be alleviated by performing concurrent
 249 computations by all swarm agents. Nevertheless a significant improvement of its computation
 250 time and path-seeking ability is clearly visible. It is a result of the added goal distance heuristic
 251 and more intuitive parameters. In this way the swarm behaviour is more easily controllable.

252 The modified RFD* algorithm however shows high potential when encountered with dynamic
 253 conditions after an initial path calculation. Table 2 presents test results collected after changing
 254 the initial goal point. In this case the ACO and RFD algorithms rely on previously collected
 255 data, i.e. on pheromone levels and node heights, respectively, modified after the first stage (for
 256 which results are shown in Table 1). The new positions of goal points were set at: (19,17) for
 257 20×20 maze, (19,8) for 20×20 mosaic, (14,9) for 20×20 alley, (49,46) for 50×50 maze, (47,22) for
 258 50×50 mosaic, (35,24) for 50×50 alley, (99,96) for 100×100 maze, (99,54) for 100×100 mosaic,
 259 and (72,49) for 100×100 alley. As for the RFD algorithm, the old goal node was given the average
 260 height of neighbouring nodes. The new goal-node height was set to, naturally, zero.

Figure 4: Localisation of new obstacles added to the testing environments (marked grey). **a**: maze. **b**: mosaic. **c**: alley.

Table 2: Averaged path length and computation time of compared algorithms after changing the goal coordinates.

		Mosaic 20×20	Alley 20×20	Maze 20×20	Mosaic 50×50	Alley 50×50	Maze 50×50	Mosaic 100×100	Alley 100×100	Maze 100×100
Path length [-]	Dijkstra	20.07	34.31	77.79	50.79	83.21	227.28	117.76	171.66	509.32
	A*	20.07	34.31	77.79	50.79	83.21	227.28	117.76	171.66	509.32
	ACO	60.45	135.32	n/a	471.88	1175.75	n/a	2651.17	5458.90	n/a
	ACO*	20.07	64.83	n/a	69.52	210.56	n/a	241.62	380.73	n/a
	RFD	28.42	98.16	n/a	295.24	798.88	n/a	2133.11	3824.62	n/a
Computation time [ms]	Dijkstra	4.658	4.655	6.215	55.931	62.062	45.988	513.412	751.669	443.453
	A*	1.953	4.375	6.326	25.148	56.548	47.941	320.462	654.803	442.611
	ACO	652.73	685.97	n/a	11139.51	10873.72	n/a	130845.01	132885.49	n/a
	ACO*	557.349	775.123	n/a	3966.235	6183.59	n/a	35302.022	28573.663	n/a
	RFD	197.364	201.56	n/a	183.474	355.38	n/a	1040.421	981.498	n/a
	RFD*	4.351	5.234	5.102	10.299	14.446	15.103	70.356	90.322	121.452

Table 3: Averaged path length and computation time of compared algorithms after addition of new obstacles.

		Mosaic 20×20	Alley 20×20	Maze 20×20	Mosaic 50×50	Alley 50×50	Maze 50×50	Mosaic 100×100	Alley 100×100	Maze 100×100
Path length [-]	Dijkstra	19.48	34.31	82.62	51.45	83.62	232.52	118.59	172.91	514.56
	A*	19.48	34.31	82.62	51.45	83.62	232.52	118.59	172.91	514.56
	ACO	49.54	112.01	n/a	438.39	1075.32	n/a	2690.44	5370.58	n/a
	ACO*	19.48	124.74	n/a	127.35	257.26	n/a	296.22	331.62	n/a
	RFD	53.88	105.43	n/a	301.66	810.58	n/a	1856.91	3788.83	n/a
Computation time [ms]	Dijkstra	5.518	4.601	5.654	67.314	85.992	57.822	557.943	753.041	440.751
	A*	2.037	4.938	5.936	28.153	55.631	47.522	362.752	637.612	434.634
	ACO	642.97	669.38	n/a	10900.92	10048.88	n/a	131001.71	133701.91	n/a
	ACO*	61.851	730.941	n/a	4928.543	6028.818	n/a	34866.798	30177.845	n/a
	RFD	120.677	581.521	n/a	804.213	1184.2	n/a	4772.492	5204.32	n/a
	RFD*	6.166	6.921	5.989	11.319	19.662	15.926	81.774	92.482	101.404

Figure 5: Marking of obstacles that have been removed from the testing environments (in gray).
a: maze. b: mosaic. c: alley.

Table 4: Averaged path length and computation time of compared algorithms after removing certain obstacles.

		Mosaic 20×20	Alley 20×20	Maze 20×20	Mosaic 50×50	Alley 50×50	Maze 50×50	Mosaic 100×100	Alley 100×100	Maze 100×100
Path length [-]	Dijkstra	17.82	32.07	76.62	48.97	79.14	224.52	115.28	167.59	504.56
	A*	17.82	32.07	76.62	48.97	79.14	224.52	115.28	167.59	504.56
	ACO	37.72	127.66	n/a	429.91	1106.74	n/a	2717.84	5129.76	n/a
	ACO*	18.65	169.39	n/a	68.48	237.54	n/a	289.69	295.25	n/a
	RFD	30.21	117.12	n/a	383.1	839.24	n/a	2196.57	4070.42	n/a
	RFD*	17.82	32.07	76.62	48.97	79.14	224.52	115.28	167.59	504.56
Computation time [ms]	Dijkstra	4.593	4.794	5.642	56.846	71.968	58.254	541.029	757.242	438.629
	A*	1.092	4.429	5.328	20.467	57.568	48.106	338.702	665.238	440.981
	ACO	643.59	667.04	n/a	10873.22	10183.79	n/a	130503.92	132996.64	n/a
	ACO*	62.35	769.54	n/a	4814.421	5924.835	n/a	32334.028	21751.601	n/a
	RFD	205.739	471.739	n/a	838.274	747.91	n/a	2572.473	1942.22	n/a
	RFD*	5.183	7.511	8.181	9.371	11.482	12.669	47.429	50.163	70.171

261 Based on the results presented in Table 2 it can be reconfirmed that the ACO algorithm
262 performs worst in all three environments. Even paths produced by the second worst algorithm –
263 the RFD – are longer than the optimum by about 1.4 to 22.3 times. This may be a result of poor
264 coefficient tuning. At this stage it is crucial for the swarm algorithms to be capable of searching
265 for new, possible paths despite already having a primary path established and reinforced. In
266 the case of the RFD algorithm some agents must be able to travel upwards a slope between two
267 nodes (i.e. to a node with negative gradient). Maladjusted values of certain algorithm coefficients
268 may hinder this ability. As for the ACO algorithm the reason for this situation may be agents
269 failing into local cycles.

270 The A* algorithm is significantly faster for small environments (by about 100 times for 20×20
271 matrices). However, the more complex the environment, the faster the RFD algorithms become
272 compared to the other two. For the 100×100 alley the A* algorithm is only about 1.4 times
273 faster. The two classical algorithms represent a polynomial time complexity, strongly related to
274 the number of nodes (with an additional heuristic dependency for the A* algorithm), while the
275 swarm algorithms perform a stochastic space search, therefore in some cases being able to rapidly
276 converge towards the goal.

277 In accordance with previous work [20] the RFD algorithms calculated new paths in a consid-
278 erably lower time. In contrast to the Dijkstra’s and A* algorithms, which must generate a path
279 over again in every case, the RFD algorithm uses information gathered in previous iterations.
280 Based on modified node heights, swarm agents are able to quickly travel across the graph and
281 search for new solutions. The RFD* algorithm exceeds in this matter. Although being still slower
282 than the two classical algorithms for small environments (A* algorithm is still about 2.2 times
283 faster for 20×20 mosaic), its advantage increases with increasing environment size. In case of the
284 100×100 alley, the RFD* algorithm performs even 7.2 times faster than the best of the other.

285 Tables 3 and 4 present results of similar tests performed after adding new obstacles (Figure 4),
286 and after removing certain obstacles from the initial environments (Figure 5). The aim of these
287 tests was to either block previously calculated optimal paths or form new, possible ones, thus
288 forcing the algorithms to adapt to new conditions. In technical terms, if an obstacle is removed or
289 added the graph connections are modified. Addition of a new obstacle severs existing neighbour
290 connections for all nodes adjacent to the new obstacle-node. Elimination of an obstacle creates
291 new connections for all adjacent nodes. As for the RFD algorithm, the newly created available

node is given the default soil amount. Likewise these tests were performed after reinforcing a first path for the starting conditions (Figure 3).

The results are similar to those obtained in previous tests. All algorithms except the original RFD and ACO were able to find optimal paths. Analogously, the RFD* algorithm exceeds the other algorithms, especially in extensive environments.

As an additional test, the algorithms were tested against introducing a major change in the environment. As opposed to the tests presented above, the major changes mean either moving the goal far from the original location, nearly on the other side of the map, or deleting a significant portion of obstacles to open entirely new, shorter paths. The mosaic map new positions of goal points were set at: (19,17) for the 20×20 map, (47,45) for the 50×50 map, and (99,85) for the 100×100 map. The other maps had their obstacles removed. Details of those changes are presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Marking of obstacles that have been removed from the testing environments (in gray) when a major change was introduced. **a**: maze. **b**: alley.

Table 5: Averaged path length and computation time of compared algorithms after removing certain obstacles when a major change was introduced.

		Mosaic 20×20	Alley 20×20	Maze 20×20	Mosaic 50×50	Alley 50×50	Maze 50×50	Mosaic 100×100	Alley 100×100	Maze 100×100
Path length [-]	Dijkstra	21.31	13	58.97	55.11	29	167.7	117.5	52	359.11
	A*	21.31	13	58.97	55.11	29	167.7	117.5	52	359.11
	ACO	85.6	238.48	n/a	506.03	1468.16	n/a	2481.27	6085.31	n/a
	ACO*	21.31	65.19	n/a	60.53	239.12	n/a	187.095	281.45	n/a
	RFD	176.27	54.01	n/a	1319.55	128.43	n/a	n/a	2616.64	n/a
	RFD*	21.31	13	58.97	55.11	29	167.7	117.5	52	359.11
Computation time [ms]	Dijkstra	2.858	2.296	3.515	30.237	30.966	28.663	226.148	305.574	229.698
	A*	0.988	0.592	3.359	11.637	3.618	28.475	112.069	16.251	226.841
	ACO	460.031	449.92	n/a	4368.948	4326.924	n/a	33090.306	33682.913	n/a
	ACO*	68.041	786.81	n/a	3303.432	5728.462	n/a	32817.862	22746.026	n/a
	RFD	686.816	966.442	n/a	4935.295	4919.252	n/a	n/a	22889.838	n/a
	RFD*	35.498	26.229	412.697	105.466	60.564	622.767	466.014	124.209	1067.273

In the case of a major change, the advantage of the RFD* algorithm is decreased. The algorithm has found appropriate paths, however, its computation time — as fast as it is — is still much slower than the Dijkstra's and A* algorithms.

In the above cases, in contrast to the ACO algorithm, the RFD algorithms benefit from information gathered in previous path calculations. Information about the environment is stored

309 as modified node heights, and can be transferred to future iterations. Therefore agents of the
310 RFD algorithms can rapidly move across a graph along reinforced paths, while still being able to
311 find new paths and adapt to small changes in the environment. This may be the case for other
312 graph-searching algorithms, e.g. the Ant Colony Optimization, however the RFD algorithm is
313 free from certain drawbacks that may cause, e.g., falling into local cycles. The ACO algorithm
314 performs very similar to the original RFD algorithm, however can be deemed as the worst of the
315 algorithms presented. This is also proof that for this particular kind of environment all swarm
316 algorithms that operate like the ACO should be modified to rival such deterministic algorithms
317 as the Dijkstra's or A*.

318 It may be noticed that the dynamic conditions proposed for the above test (i.e., removal and
319 addition of obstacles) are based on minor changes in the environment. The idea behind this is
320 that real-world environments change likewise on a basic level. In most cases all bigger changes can
321 be divided into smaller, incremental changes. In fact, if the changes in the environment is more
322 substantial (e.g., when a new optimal path on the other side of the map would be opened) the
323 highlighted advantages of the RFD algorithm would not matter so much because the algorithm
324 would have to compute an entirely new path from the beginning. Therefore the system presented
325 at this stage is not versatile.

326 It is apparent that the test do not provide full potential of the RFD algorithm. As a heuristic
327 swarm algorithm, it can be modified to work with problems of a greater complexity. It is possible
328 to add and test another layer of restrictions and more fitness functions according to a more
329 complex model of an environment (e.g. with varying terrain height). Additional time, velocity, or
330 acceleration optimisation using the RFD algorithm should be the topic of future research.

331 4 Conclusions

332 This paper presents a comparison of the River Formation Dynamics algorithm and its modified
333 versions with the Ant Colony Optimization algorithm, its modified version, and two classical
334 Dijkstra's and A* algorithms based on their optimised path lengths and computation times. The
335 original River Formation Dynamics algorithm was modified to increase its convergence towards a
336 solution. During its operation, a set of agents-drops explores the environment in search for the
337 best path from a starting node to an objective. While searching for a solution, agents modify node
338 heights, which helps to create stronger tendencies towards a given goal. Moreover, properties of
339 the algorithm (in particular, relying on gradient between nodes) ensure its resistance to local
340 cycles.

341 The results obtained in this study have shown that modern swarm algorithms provide an
342 alternative in the process of dynamic path planning to conventional, heuristic and complete graph
343 algorithms, such as the Dijkstra's and A*. Superiority of the proposed, modified River Formation
344 Dynamics algorithm is apparent for complex environments with an increasing number of cells, while
345 in some cases its calculations are over 13 times faster than the fastest conventional A* algorithm.
346 Moreover, the time of trajectory planning in case of dynamic changes in the environment is in
347 the range of about 70–121 ms, which allows its use in real-time systems. However, further work
348 is needed in order to make the path generation time comparable to conventional algorithms
349 for completely unknown environments. A solution to this problem would be to use some other
350 algorithm (e.g., Dijkstra's or A*) in the first iteration for an unknown environment, while in
351 the later phases use the modified River Formation Dynamics algorithm. Another solution for
352 improving the computation times would be to perform concurrent computations by all swarm
353 agents.

354 Further work is also required to verify the applicability of swarm algorithms, such as the

355 modified River Formation Dynamics, to generate paths in partly unknown environments. Given
356 the described research, such work is justified, and the results may be promising.

357 References

- 358 [1] D.-J. Huh et al. “Path planning and navigation for autonomous mobile robot”. In: *IECON*
359 *02 [Industrial Electronics Society, IEEE 2002 28th Annual Conference of the]*. Vol. 2. Nov.
360 2002, pp. 1538–1542. DOI: [10.1109/IECON.2002.1185508](https://doi.org/10.1109/IECON.2002.1185508).
- 361 [2] N. Sariff and N. Buniyamin. “An Overview of Autonomous Mobile Robot Path Planning
362 Algorithms”. In: *Research and Development, 2006. SCORed 2006. 4th Student Conference*
363 *on*. June 2006, pp. 183–188. DOI: [10.1109/SCORED.2006.4339335](https://doi.org/10.1109/SCORED.2006.4339335).
- 364 [3] H. Wang, Y. Yu, and Q. Yuan. “Application of Dijkstra algorithm in robot path-planning”.
365 In: *Mechanic Automation and Control Engineering (MACE), 2011 Second International*
366 *Conference on*. July 2011, pp. 1067–1069. DOI: [10.1109/MACE.2011.5987118](https://doi.org/10.1109/MACE.2011.5987118).
- 367 [4] E. Masehian and D. Sedighzadeh. “Classic and Heuristic Approaches in Robot Motion
368 Planning – A Chronological Review”. In: *International Journal of Mechanical, Aerospace,*
369 *Industrial and Mechatronics Engineering* 1.2 (2007), pp. 249–254. ISSN: 1307-6892.
- 370 [5] M. P. Garcia et al. “Path planning for autonomous mobile robot navigation with ant
371 colony optimization and fuzzy cost function evaluation”. In: *Applied Soft Computing* 9.3
372 (2009), pp. 1102–1110. ISSN: 1568-4946. DOI: [10.1016/j.asoc.2009.02.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2009.02.014). URL:
373 <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1568494609000349>.
- 374 [6] C. Lum and R. Rysdyk. “Time constrained randomized path planning using spatial net-
375 works”. In: *American Control Conference*. June 2008, pp. 3725–3732. DOI: [10.1109/ACC.](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACC.2008.4587073)
376 [2008.4587073](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACC.2008.4587073).
- 377 [7] H. Li, S. X. Yang, and M. Seto. “Neural-Network-Based Path Planning for a Multirobot
378 System With Moving Obstacles”. In: *Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part C: Applications*
379 *and Reviews, IEEE Transactions on* 39.4 (July 2009), pp. 410–419. ISSN: 1094-6977. DOI:
380 [10.1109/TSMCC.2009.2020789](https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMCC.2009.2020789).
- 381 [8] A. Yahja, S. Singh, and A. Stentz. “An Efficient On-line Path Planner for Outdoor Mobile
382 Robots Operating in Vast Environments”. In: *Robotics and Autonomous Systems* 33.2/3
383 (Aug. 2000), pp. 129–143.
- 384 [9] D. Ferguson and A. Stentz. “Field D*: An Interpolation-Based Path Planner and Replanner”.
385 In: *Robotics Research*. Ed. by S. Thrun, R. Brooks, and H. Durrant-Whyte. Vol. 28. Springer
386 Tracts in Advanced Robotics. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2007, pp. 239–253. ISBN: 978-3-540-
387 48110-2. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-540-48113-3_22](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-48113-3_22). URL: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-](http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-48113-3_22)
388 [3-540-48113-3_22](http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-48113-3_22).
- 389 [10] H. Liu, W. Wan, and H. Zha. “A dynamic subgoal path planner for unpredictable environ-
390 nments”. In: *Robotics and Automation (ICRA), 2010 IEEE International Conference on*.
391 May 2010, pp. 994–1001. DOI: [10.1109/ROBOT.2010.5509324](https://doi.org/10.1109/ROBOT.2010.5509324).
- 392 [11] H. I. Kang, B. Lee, and K. Kim. “Path Planning Algorithm Using the Particle Swarm
393 Optimization and the Improved Dijkstra Algorithm”. In: *Computational Intelligence and*
394 *Industrial Application, 2008. PACIIA '08. Pacific-Asia Workshop on*. Vol. 2. Dec. 2008,
395 pp. 1002–1004. DOI: [10.1109/PACIIA.2008.376](https://doi.org/10.1109/PACIIA.2008.376).

- 396 [12] Y. Zhang, D.-w. Gong, and J.-h. Zhang. “Robot path planning in uncertain environ-
397 ment using multi-objective particle swarm optimization”. In: *Neurocomputing* 103 (2013),
398 pp. 172–185. ISSN: 0925-2312. DOI: [10.1016/j.neucom.2012.09.019](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2012.09.019). URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0925231212007722>.
399
- 400 [13] Y. Wang, I. Sillitoe, and D. Mulvaney. “Mobile Robot Path Planning in Dynamic Environ-
401 ments”. In: *Robotics and Automation, 2007 IEEE International Conference on*. Apr. 2007,
402 pp. 71–76. DOI: [10.1109/ROBOT.2007.363767](https://doi.org/10.1109/ROBOT.2007.363767).
- 403 [14] C.-M. Lin. “Multicriteria–multistage planning for the optimal path selection using hybrid
404 genetic algorithms”. In: *Applied Mathematics and Computation* 180.2 (2006), pp. 549–558.
405 ISSN: 0096-3003. DOI: [10.1016/j.amc.2005.12.048](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amc.2005.12.048). URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0096300306000439>.
406
- 407 [15] H. Miao and Y.-C. Tian. “Dynamic robot path planning using an enhanced simulated
408 annealing approach”. In: *Applied Mathematics and Computation* 222 (2013), pp. 420–437.
409 ISSN: 0096-3003. DOI: [10.1016/j.amc.2013.07.022](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amc.2013.07.022). URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0096300313007728>.
410
- 411 [16] B. Mohajer et al. “A New Online Random Particles Optimization Algorithm for Mobile
412 Robot Path Planning in Dynamic Environments”. In: *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*
413 2013 (2013), p. 9. DOI: [10.1155/2013/491346](https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/491346). URL: <http://www.hindawi.com/journals/mpe/2013/491346/abs/>.
414
- 415 [17] P. Rabanal, I. Rodriguez, and F. Rubio. “Using River Formation Dynamics to Design
416 Heuristic Algorithms”. In: *Unconventional Computation*. Ed. by S. G. Akl et al. Vol. 4618.
417 Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2007, pp. 163–177. ISBN:
418 978-3-540-73553-3. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-540-73554-0_16](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-73554-0_16). URL: http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-73554-0_16.
419
- 420 [18] P. Rabanal, I. Rodriguez, and F. Rubio. “Solving Dynamic TSP by Using River Formation
421 Dynamics”. In: *2008 Fourth International Conference on Natural Computation*. Vol. 1.
422 IEEE, 2008, pp. 246–250. ISBN: 978-0-7695-3304-9. DOI: [10.1109/ICNC.2008.760](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICNC.2008.760). URL:
423 <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/lpdocs/epic03/wrapper.htm?arnumber=4666848>.
- 424 [19] P. Rabanal, I. Rodriguez, and F. Rubio. “Applying River Formation Dynamics to Solve NP-
425 Complete Problems”. In: *Nature-Inspired Algorithms for Optimisation*. Ed. by R. Chiong.
426 Vol. 193. Studies in Computational Intelligence. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2009, pp. 333–
427 368. ISBN: 978-3-642-00266-3. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-642-00267-0_12](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-00267-0_12). URL: http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-00267-0_12.
428
- 429 [20] G. Redlarski, A. Palkowski, and M. Dabkowski. “Using River Formation Dynamics Algorithm
430 in Mobile Robot Navigation”. In: *Solid State Phenom.* 198 (2013), pp. 138–143. ISSN: 1662-
431 9779. DOI: [10.4028/www.scientific.net/SSP.198.138](https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/SSP.198.138). URL: <http://www.scientific.net/SSP.198.138>.
432
- 433 [21] E. Dijkstra. “A note on two problems in connexion with graphs”. In: *Numerische Mathematik*
434 1.1 (1959), pp. 269–271. ISSN: 0029-599X. DOI: [10.1007/BF01386390](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01386390). URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF01386390>.
435
- 436 [22] P. Hart, N. Nilsson, and B. Raphael. “A Formal Basis for the Heuristic Determination of
437 Minimum Cost Paths”. In: *Systems Science and Cybernetics, IEEE Transactions on* 4.2
438 (July 1968), pp. 100–107. ISSN: 0536-1567. DOI: [10.1109/TSSC.1968.300136](https://doi.org/10.1109/TSSC.1968.300136).
- 439 [23] M. Dorigo, M. Birattari, and T. Stutzle. “Ant colony optimization”. In: *Computational*
440 *Intelligence Magazine, IEEE* 1.4 (2006), pp. 28–39. DOI: [10.1109/MCI.2006.329691](https://doi.org/10.1109/MCI.2006.329691). URL:
441 <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/articleDetails.jsp?arnumber=4129846>.